

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. R. H. Thomson for a sample of 1-hydroxy-2-methyl anthraquinone, Dr. Michio Takido for a sample of obtusifolin and Dr. M. H. Simatupung for the samples of dehydrotectol and tectol.

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Chemical Investigation of Indigenous Plant Resources

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*Manuscript received 6 April 1978, revised 2 January 1979,
accepted 4 August 1979*

THE present communication deals with the chemical investigation of *Pogestemon placranthoides* and *Hedychium coronarium*.

The plant *Hedychium coronarium* belongs¹ to family Scitamineae and is distributed throughout India. This plant is reported^{2,3} to be very useful in paper making. It is also endowed with a number of medicinal properties⁴.

The plant *Pogestemon placranthoides* belongs⁵ to family Labiatae and is known⁶ to have good therapeutic utility. The use is made⁷ of the plant ash as manure in paddy crop.

The preliminary pharmacological screening of the oil obtained from pet-ether extract of *Pogestemon placranthoides* revealed significant CNS depressant activity. This observation was substantiated by potentiation of sleeping time induced by hexobarbitone.

The oil from the pet-ether extract of *P. placranthoides* bracts gave, (i) an aliphatic hydrocarbon C₃₀H₆₂, m.p. 65°, (ii) Phytol, identified by comparison (IR) with an authentic specimen, (iii) Vanillin and (iv) 4-hydroxy-4-methyl-pentane-2-one, b.p. 54-60°/10 mm, NMR, 4 singlets at δ 1.2 (6H), 2.17 (3H), 2.6 (2H) and 3.92 (1H).

The presence of free phytol can be very significant in the light of its role⁸ in the formation of Vit. K and anti-haemorrhagic activity possessed by the plant.

The comparison of the structure of 4-hydroxy-4-methyl-pentane-2-one with the known⁹ biogenic precursors for terpenes made it immediately evident that this compound could also provide a sound base for the speculation on its nature as a building block in terpene synthesis.

Potassium chloride isolated from alcohol extract of the stems can account for the use of stem ash as manure in paddy crop.

The yellowish brown oil obtained from the rhizomes of *Hedychium coronarium*, by pet-ether extraction followed by steam distillation showed, $d_{20} 0.9439$; $n_D 1.501$; $[\alpha]_D +1.20'$; acid no. 7.73; ester No. 20.3. These constants differ from the constants given¹⁰⁻¹³, for the oil obtained by direct steam distillation of the plant material.

The column chromatography of ethanol extract of rhizomes of *Hedychium coronarium* afforded a furanoid diterpene, hedychanone, m.p. 134°, C₂₀H₂₆O₂. The IR, NMR and mass spectra agree well with those reported in literature¹⁴.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their thanks to Dr. Grewal, Director, CIBA Research Centre, Goregaon; for IR, NMR and Mass Spectra. One of the authors (ANB) is also thankful to U. G. C. for the award of JRF.

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N-Acridin-5-yl-N'-Aryloxyacetyl Hydrazines as Possible Fungicides

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Manuscript received 6 March 1979, accepted 4 August 1979

Chemical Examination of the Seeds of *Cassia laevigata*

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*Manuscript received 27 February 1978,
accepted 4 August 1979*

FROM the hot ethanolic extract of the seeds of *Cassia laevigata* two anthraquinones, chrysophanol (I) and physcion(II) and a flavonoid, quercetin 3,7-di-rhamnopyranoside(III) have been isolated and studied.

Compound (I), m.p. 195°, $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$, has been shown to be 1,8-di-hydroxy-3-methyl-anthraquinone (chrysophanol) and compound (II) m.p. 207°, $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ characterised as 1,8-di-hydroxy-6-methoxy-3-methyl-anthraquinone (physcion), by analysis, colour reactions, spectral data, degradation studies and derivatization.

The third compound m.p. 190° (d), $C_{27}H_{20}O_{17}$, on hydrolysis gave quercetin ($C_{15}H_{10}O_7$) and rhamnose. The position of the rhamnose units have been shown to be with the 3- and 7-hydroxyls by colour reactions¹ and spectral shift^{2,3}. The rhamnose units are present in the pyranose form as proved by periodate oxidation⁴ and the glycosidic linkages as α -, confirmed by its hydrolysis with takadiastase.

All the three compounds are known to occur in plants particularly in the genus *Cassia*.

Acknowledgement

One of us (A.R.) expresses her grateful thanks to CSIR for a Senior Research Fellowship.

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ALTHOUGH an unsubstituted nucleus containing heterocyclic nitrogen is seldom fungitoxic, acridine is known to be toxic to spores of various rusts¹. Horsfall and Rich² found acridine to be fairly active against *Sclerotinia fructicola* and *Macrosporium sarcinaeforme*. Acridines have been found to act as insecticides³⁻⁵, fungicides^{2,6}, bactericides⁷, medicinals⁸ and carcinogenic⁹ compounds.

We have therefore synthesised N-acridin-5-yl-N'-aryloxyacetyl hydrazines and screened some of them for their fungicidal activity against *A. flavus* and *H. oryzae*.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected.

N-Acridin-5-yl-N'-aryloxyacetyl hydrazines(I) :

A methanolic solution of a substituted-5-chloro-acridine¹⁰ (0.002 M) and an aryloxy acetyl hydrazine¹¹ (0.002 M) was refluxed gently for three hrs and cooled. The product separating out was filtered and recrystallised.

The compounds thus prepared, have been listed in Table 1.

Fungicidal Activity :

Twenty-one of these compounds were screened for their antifungal activity against *A. flavus* and *H. oryzae* by agar plate technique¹² and found to be moderately active. The most active compounds were found to contain a naphthoxy ring. A change in the position of ethoxy group did not show any effect towards antifungal activity. Halogenated compounds possessed a bit higher fungicidal activity.